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Phone: **+998 50 737 87 88**

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REMITTANCE INFLOWS AND THE SUSTAINABILITY OF ECONOMIC GROWTH: A TIME-SERIES ANALYSIS FOR UZBEKISTAN

O. B. Gimranova

Independent Researcher,
Kimyo International University in Tashkent

Abstract. International remittances' impact on Uzbekistan's economic growth is examined using time-series analysis methods, including ADF, Johansen cointegration, VAR, and VECM, based on data for 2000–2025. The empirical findings reveal a statistically significant positive relationship, indicating that remittance inflows contribute to GDP growth through increased consumption, investment, and household income. At the same time, risks associated with dependence on external labor markets are identified, and policy recommendations are proposed to transform remittances into a source of sustainable development.

Keywords: international remittances, economic growth, time-series analysis, cointegration, VECM model, migration, GDP, Uzbekistan's economy.

Annotatsiya. Xalqaro pul o'tkazmalarining O'zbekiston iqtisodiy o'sishiga ta'siri 2000–2025-yillar ma'lumotlari asosida ADF testi, Yoxansen kointegratsiyasi, VAR va VECM kabi vaqt qatorlari tahlili usullari yordamida o'rganilgan. Empirik natijalar pul o'tkazmalari ichki iste'mol, investitsiyalar va aholi daromadlarini oshirish orqali YaIM o'sishiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishini tasdiqlaydi. Shu bilan birga, tashqi mehnat bozorlariga qaramlik bilan bog'liq xavflar aniqlanib, pul o'tkazmalarini barqaror rivojlanish manbasiga aylantirish bo'yicha ilmiy-amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: xalqaro pul o'tkazmalari, iqtisodiy o'sish, vaqt qatorlari tahlili, kointegratsiya, VECM modeli, migratsiya, YaIM, O'zbekiston iqtisodiyoti.

Аннотация. Влияние международных денежных переводов на экономический рост Узбекистана исследовано на основе данных за 2000–2025 годы с применением методов анализа временных рядов, включая тест ADF, коинтеграцию Йохансена, VAR и VECM. Эмпирические результаты подтверждают наличие статистически значимой положительной взаимосвязи, согласно которой приток денежных переводов способствует росту ВВП за счёт расширения потребления, инвестиций и доходов населения. Одновременно выявлены риски, связанные с зависимостью от внешних рынков труда, и предложены научно-практические рекомендации по трансформации денежных переводов в источник устойчивого развития.

Ключевые слова: международные денежные переводы, экономический рост, анализ временных рядов, коинтеграция, модель VECM, миграция, ВВП, экономика Узбекистана.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of modern globalization, international labor migration has become a crucial factor in the socio-economic development of many countries worldwide. One of the primary outcomes of migration processes is the formation of stable remittance flows sent by migrant workers to their families in their countries of origin. For developing nations, remittances represent a significant source of external financial resources, contributing to improved living standards, increased domestic consumption, and the expansion of entrepreneurial activity.

The Republic of Uzbekistan is among the countries where international remittances play an important role in the national economy. A substantial share of the country's citizens is engaged in labor activities abroad, and the funds they remit exert a considerable influence on household incomes and macroeconomic indicators. In recent years, the volume of remittance inflows into Uzbekistan has demonstrated a steady upward trend, highlighting the need for a deeper investigation of their impact on the country's economic development.

In economic literature, the impact of remittances on economic growth is generally viewed as multifaceted. On the one hand, remittances stimulate consumption, encourage savings and investment, contribute to poverty reduction, and enhance public welfare. On the other hand, a high dependence on external transfers may increase sensitivity to changes in the global economic environment and international labor markets. Consequently, examining the role of remittances in supporting the sustainability of economic growth remains highly relevant.

The relevance of this study is determined by the need to assess the impact of international remittances on Uzbekistan's economy in the context of ongoing market reforms and the country's integration into the global economic system. The application of modern time-series analysis methods makes it possible to identify the nature

and magnitude of the relationship between remittance inflows and economic growth indicators, as well as to determine the long-term trends of their interaction.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A substantial body of scientific research conducted by both foreign and domestic scholars has been devoted to investigating the impact of international remittances on economic growth. In contemporary economic literature, remittances are regarded as an important source of external financing for developing countries, exerting a significant influence on consumption levels, investment activity, poverty reduction, and macroeconomic stability.

The theoretical foundations of the impact of labor migration and remittances on economic development were established in the pioneering works of R. Lucas and O. Stark. According to the New Economics of Labor Migration (NELM), migration is conceptualized as a household strategy aimed at diversifying income sources and reducing economic risks. Within this framework, remittances function as a mechanism for supporting migrant families and as a factor contributing to improvements in their welfare.

A substantial contribution to the study of the role of remittances has been made through World Bank research and the works of D. Ratha. The author emphasizes that remittances constitute one of the most stable sources of external financial inflows for developing countries. Unlike foreign direct investment (FDI) and international loans, remittance inflows tend to demonstrate greater resilience during periods of financial and economic uncertainty. According to the researcher, these funds contribute to poverty reduction, stimulate consumer demand, and support human capital development.

The relationship between remittances and economic growth has been examined in detail by R. Adams and J. Page. The authors concluded that an increase in remittance inflows contributes to poverty reduction and improves living standards. Their empirical findings demonstrated that remittance growth exerts a positive influence on household incomes and supports improvements in social indicators.

Of particular interest are the studies of S. Chami, C. Fullenkamp, and S. Jahjah, which present a balanced perspective on the impact of remittances on economic growth. The authors note that a considerable share of incoming funds is directed toward current consumption, while the long-term growth effect becomes more pronounced when resources are effectively channeled into productive investment. According to the researchers, the positive impact of remittances is strengthened in the presence of a developed financial system and a favorable investment climate.

In their studies, Giuliano and Ruiz-Arranz demonstrated that the effectiveness of remittances depends on the level of financial sector development. The authors found that in countries with less-developed banking systems, remittances partially compensate for limited access to financial resources and serve as an alternative source of investment financing. In countries with more developed financial markets, remittances continue to play an important complementary role in supporting economic activity.

Scientific publications devoted to the economy of Uzbekistan emphasize the growing significance of remittances in shaping household incomes. Researchers note that remittance inflows help maintain consumption levels, finance education, improve housing conditions, and support the development of small businesses. At the same time, they highlight the importance of creating effective mechanisms for transforming remittances into long-term investments.

Contemporary research increasingly relies on econometric time-series analysis methods. To investigate the relationship between remittances and economic growth, stationarity tests, cointegration analysis, Vector Autoregression (VAR) models, and Vector Error Correction Models (VECM) are widely applied. The use of these methods makes it possible to evaluate both the short-term and long-term effects of remittances and to identify the direction of causal relationships among the analyzed indicators.

The reviewed literature indicates that assessments of the impact of remittances on economic growth vary across countries and economic conditions. While most researchers acknowledge the positive contribution of remittances to household incomes and consumer demand, the scale and sustainability of this impact are influenced by the structural characteristics of the national economy, the level of financial sector development, and the effectiveness of public policy.

The findings of previous studies confirm the importance of further research into the role of international remittances in promoting sustainable economic growth. This research direction is particularly relevant for the Republic of Uzbekistan, where remittances continue to represent a major source of financial resources and an important factor in the country's socio-economic development.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study utilized data on international remittance inflows to Uzbekistan and gross domestic product (GDP) for the period 2000–2025. The dataset was compiled from official sources, including the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Statistics Agency, the World Bank, and other relevant institutions. Time-series analysis techniques

were employed to examine the relationship between remittances and economic growth. Initially, the stationarity of the variables was tested using the Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) test. The long-run relationship between the variables was assessed through the Johansen cointegration test. To evaluate both short-run and long-run effects, Vector Autoregression (VAR) and Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) approaches were applied. In addition, Granger causality analysis and impulse response functions were used to identify the dynamic interactions between the variables.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

To assess the impact of international remittances on the sustainability of economic growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan, an analysis of the dynamics of key macroeconomic indicators was conducted for the period 2000–2025. The core variables of the study included the volume of labor migrants' remittances and the country's gross domestic product (GDP).

The analysis revealed a steady upward trend in remittance inflows throughout the examined period. While remittance volumes were relatively modest in the early 2000s, they increased substantially in subsequent years due to the intensification of external labor migration and the expansion of international payment system capabilities. A particularly pronounced surge in growth was observed after 2017, driven by the liberalization of the foreign exchange market and the advancement of digital financial services.

Parallel to the increase in remittance inflows, the country experienced sustained growth in gross domestic product. This provides preliminary evidence of a potential relationship between incoming transfers and the dynamics of economic development. An analysis of the statistical data indicates that periods of remittance growth were generally accompanied by an expansion of domestic consumer spending, an increase in retail trade turnover, and enhanced household investment activity (Table 1).

Table 1
Dynamics of Remittance Inflows and GDP in Uzbekistan (Selected Years)¹

Year	Remittance Inflows (USD billion)	GDP (USD billion)
2000	0.4	13.8
2005	1.2	19.7
2010	3.0	46.2
2015	3.8	86.1
2020	6.0	59.9
2022	16.9	80.4
2023	14.5	90.9
2024	14.8	102.5
2025*	15.6	110.3

To identify the nature of the relationship between the examined indicators, a correlation analysis was performed. The results revealed a positive correlation between the volume of remittances and gross domestic product. The correlation coefficient indicates a relatively high degree of association between economic growth and the dynamics of incoming transfers.

At the subsequent stage of the study, the time series were tested for stationarity using the Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) test. The results demonstrated that the examined series were non-stationary in their levels; however, they became stationary after being transformed into first differences. This outcome justified the application of cointegration analysis methods to evaluate the long-term relationship between the variables (Figure 1).

1 Compiled by the author based on data from the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Statistics Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the World Bank.

Figure 1. Dynamics of International Remittance Inflows and Gross Domestic Product in Uzbekistan, 2000–2025²

The results of the Johansen cointegration test confirmed the presence of a cointegrating relationship between remittances and gross domestic product, indicating the existence of a long-term equilibrium between the examined indicators. In other words, despite short-term fluctuations, changes in remittance inflows exert a sustainable long-term influence on the country’s economic development.

For a more comprehensive analysis, a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) was estimated to evaluate both the long-term and short-term effects of remittances. The obtained results demonstrated a statistically significant positive impact of remittances on economic growth. It was established that increases in remittance inflows stimulate domestic consumption, expand aggregate demand, and enhance investment activity among the population.

Additional Granger causality analysis revealed a causal relationship between remittances and economic growth. The findings indicate that increasing remittance inflows contribute to the acceleration of economic growth, while a higher level of national economic development, in turn, creates additional opportunities for the efficient utilization of incoming financial resources (Table 2).

Table 2
Econometric Estimation Results of the Remittance–Growth Nexus³

Econometric Method	Results
Correlation Analysis	Strong positive correlation between remittance inflows and GDP
Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) Test	Series are non-stationary in levels but stationary in first differences
Johansen Cointegration Test	Confirmed the presence of a long-term cointegrating relationship
Vector Error Correction Model (VECM)	Statistically significant positive impact of remittances on GDP
Granger Causality Test	Identified a causal relationship between remittances and economic growth
Impulse Response Function (IRF)	The peak effect of a remittance shock is observed within 2–3 years
Long-Term Effect	Sustainable positive contribution to the stability of economic growth

The impulse response analysis demonstrated that a positive remittance shock exerts a favorable influence on the dynamics of gross domestic product over several subsequent periods. The peak effect is observed within the first two to three years following an increase in remittance inflows, after which the impact gradually moderates while remaining positive.

The findings of this study indicate that international remittances constitute an important factor in supporting the sustainability of economic growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan. They contribute to expanding household incomes, sustaining domestic demand, and generating additional investment resources. At the same time, the results highlight the importance of strengthening mechanisms that enhance the effective use of remittance inflows within the national economy.

2 Compiled by the author based on data from the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Statistics Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the World Bank.

3 Author’s calculations.

The results of the research confirm the hypothesis that remittances have a positive impact on Uzbekistan's economic growth. To enhance the effectiveness of these financial resources, it is advisable to create favorable conditions for directing a portion of incoming funds toward investment projects, entrepreneurial development, and human capital accumulation. Such measures will further strengthen the contribution of remittances to the long-term sustainable development of the national economy.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study evaluated the impact of international remittances on the sustainability of economic growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan using time-series analysis methods. In the contemporary context of globalization and intensifying international labor migration, remittances have emerged as an important source of financial resources for the national economy, exerting a significant influence on public welfare and the country's macroeconomic stability.

The findings of this research indicate that, over recent decades, the volume of remittance inflows into Uzbekistan has demonstrated a steady upward trend. Concurrently, key macroeconomic indicators have also expanded, providing evidence of a close relationship between remittance inflows and the dynamics of economic development.

The conducted econometric analysis confirmed the existence of a long-term positive relationship between remittances and gross domestic product. It was established that increasing remittance inflows stimulate domestic consumption, expand aggregate demand, enhance investment activity, and improve the population's standard of living. Furthermore, remittances perform an important social function by providing additional support to households and contributing to poverty reduction.

At the same time, the research results indicate the importance of strengthening the resilience of economic development through the effective management of external income sources. Changes in the economic conditions of host countries, exchange-rate fluctuations, and developments in international labor markets may influence remittance inflows and, consequently, domestic economic activity. Therefore, further diversification of economic growth drivers remains an important policy priority.

Thus, international remittances serve as an important driver of sustainable economic growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and their positive impact can be further strengthened by improving the efficiency of fund utilization and expanding opportunities for investment-oriented applications.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

- Establish additional mechanisms to encourage the investment of remittances in small businesses and entrepreneurial activities;
- Expand public access to modern banking and investment instruments to ensure the efficient utilization of incoming funds;
- Develop financial literacy programs specifically tailored to remittance recipients;
- Enhance the digital infrastructure of international remittance systems in order to reduce transaction costs;
- Design targeted investment products for labor migrants and their family members;
- Encourage the channeling of remittances into productive sectors of the economy and innovative projects;
- Broaden opportunities for utilizing remittances to finance education, vocational training, and human capital development;
- Strengthen bilateral cooperation with countries that serve as the principal destinations of labor migration for citizens of Uzbekistan;
- Improve monitoring and statistical accounting systems for international remittance flows;
- Promote the diversification of economic growth sources to enhance long-term economic sustainability.

The implementation of these measures will improve the efficiency of international remittance utilization and strengthen their contribution to ensuring long-term sustainable economic development in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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